

APPENDIX A
CASE STUDY

This section presents a comparative case study between our model and baseline models, highlighting performance differences in handling code format issues, code refactoring, and bug fixing. Figure 1 illustrates specific instances where our model outperforms the baselines, providing visual evidence of its superior capabilities.

Discussion_r621049553 (Code Format Issues)
<p>M_{base}: (executeUpdate) ... int updateCount = executeMutation(stmt); ...</p> <p>M_{assoc}: (executeUpdate) ... int updateCount = executeMutation(stmt, createQueryLogger(stmt,sql)); ...</p> <p>The Ground Truth: "nit: space after comma"</p> <p>Tufano: "Is this correct?"</p> <p>AUGER: "what be the reason for this change"</p> <p>CommentFinder: "you could use a try-with-resource here"</p> <p>CodeReviewer: "Why not pass the logger in executeMutation?"</p> <p>Ours: "nit: space after comma"</p> <p>Response in Real: [a commit including adding space]</p>
Discussion_r218927752 (Code Refactoring)
<p>M_{base}: (verifySerialization) ... assertThat(row).isEqualTo(copy); ...</p> <p>M_{assoc}: (getDate) ... assertThat(resultSet.getDate(0)).compareTo(Date.fromYearMonthDay(2018, 5, 29)) == 0); ...</p> <p>The Ground Truth: "assertThat(resultSet.getDate(0)).isEqualTo(Date.fromYearMonthDay(2018, 5, 29))"</p> <p>Tufano: "Wondering if we should tests tests here: a)"</p> <p>AUGER: "assertSame(resultSet.getDate(0)).compareTo(Date.fromYearMonthDay(2018, 5, 29)) == 0);"</p> <p>CommentFinder: "add a test date with different year and date more than a month apart"</p> <p>CodeReviewer: "Can the Zoned.of("UTC") reference can be replaced with ZoneOffset.UTC?"</p> <p>CodeReviewer: "This test is failing on the latest branch. It should be: consumer.onPartialResultSet(PartialResultSet.newBuilder().setMetadata(Type.struct(Type.StructField.of("T", Type.int64()))).addValues(Value.int64(Long.MIN_VALUE)).toProto()).addValues(Value.int64(Long.MAX_VALUE)).toProto()).build();"</p> <p>Ours: "assertThat(resultSet.getDate(0)).isEqualTo(Date.fromYearMonthDay(2018, 5, 29))"</p> <p>Response in Real: [a commit with commit message "Use isEqualTo() for getDateList()"]</p>
Discussion_r156281606 (Bug Fixing)
<p>M_{base}: (getGenericRowDelimitedSerde) private static Serde<GenericRow> getGenericRowDelimitedSerde(...</p> <p>M_{assoc}: (getSchemaFromAvro) public static synchronized Schema getSchemaFromAvro(...</p> <p>The Ground Truth: "Why synchronized?"</p> <p>Tufano: "you should import avroSchema and use the fully qualified name of the field instead of the schema name."</p> <p>AUGER: "typo schema to a greater extent more common for a declarative schema"</p> <p>CommentFinder: "same idea here w/ recreating the reader"</p> <p>CodeReviewer: "Nit: I think it's better to use a static import for this method."</p> <p>Ours: "Why synchronized?"</p> <p>Response in Real: Actually you are right. No shared variables among threads. Removed synchronized.</p>

Fig. 1. Case study highlighting code format issues, code refactoring, and bug fixing, demonstrating the superior capabilities of our model compared to baselines.

APPENDIX B
COMPLETE EXPERIMENT RESULTS

This section includes comprehensive results not listed in the main paper, encompassing analyses on complete factor combination settings and extended results on the $CRCN_{long}$ dataset.

A. Complete Factor Combination Settings

Given the complexity and breadth of our experiments, including numerous factors and their different representations, it is impractical to detail every combination in the main text. Here we list the complete settings as shown in Table I. Subsequent sections provide detailed results for these settings.

Here is the full name of each abbreviation:

- ID: Setting ID.
- OCS: Original Code Snippet / Code Changes.
- RT: Review Tags.
- LBI: Line Breaks and Indentatons.
- VC: Vanilla Concatenation.
- VC-Side: Vanilla Concatenation with optional tokens.
- LGD: Line-grained Difference.

- LGD-End: Line-grained Difference with optional tokens.
- SGD: Span-grained Difference.
- SGD-End: Span-grained Difference with optional tokens.
- BT: Block Tags.
- ST: Single-line Tags.

B. Complete Results for Factor Combinations on $CRCN_{short}$

Table II presents complete outcomes for the $CRCN_{short}$ dataset under various modeling settings and paradigms. Results are organized by IDs (corresponding to the settings in Table I), syntactic similarity measures (BLEU-4, ROUGE-L, METEOR), and semantic similarity measures (BERTScore Precision, Recall, and F1-score), rescaled using the scoring baseline of "microsoft/deberta-xlarge-mnli". Results from GPT-4 are marked with * and are based on a subset of 1000 random samples. This nuanced analysis helps illuminate the specific impacts of different settings.

C. Complete Results for Factor Combinations on $CRCN_{long}$

Further analysis on $CRCN_{long}$ is shown in Table III. Here, the left and right parts of the table correspond to the two mainstream paradigms discussed in the main paper.

D. Complete Results for Code Change Structure Graph

Tables VI and VII detail the impacts of integrating the code change structure graph under selected settings for the $CRCN_{short}$ and $CRCN_{long}$ datasets, respectively.

E. Complete Results for Comparison with Baselines

Table VIII showcases our top results compared to the baselines. Notably, the best values for each metric are reported under specific settings, differing slightly from those in the main paper.

F. Average Token Length for Factor Combinations

Tables IV and V detail the average token lengths across various settings on the $CRCN_{short}$ and $CRCN_{long}$ datasets. The color intensity of each cell indicates the value, with darker shades denoting higher token counts. These tables provide a clear visual representation of how different factors and their representations influence token length, aiding in understanding the computational efficiency and complexity of each model configuration.

In $CRCN_{short}$, the review tag has a minimal impact on token length, showing an increase of approximately 0.02. Among the different methods of incorporating code changes, the span-grained difference results in the least increase of 0.11, followed by line-grained difference and vanilla concatenation with increases of 0.22 and 0.24, respectively. The VC-side variant contributes an additional 0.04, attributed to the inclusion of two pairs of special tokens. Additionally, the LGD-End and Span-End variants add 0.12 and 0.03, respectively. The incorporation of line breaks also contributes to increased token lengths, with the increase varying depending on the mode of code incorporation (0.29, 0.25, 0.24). In the case of $CRCN_{long}$, the relative additional token lengths for line and span-grained differences decrease, while that of vanilla concatenation experiences an increase.

TABLE I
MODELING SETTINGS WITH DIFFERENT COMBINATIONS OF REPRESENTATIONS.

ID	OCS	RT	LBI	ID	OCS	RT	LBI	ID	OCS	RT	LBI	ID	OCS	RT	LBI
V1	VC-Side	BT	✓	L1	LGD-End	BT	✓	S1	SGD-End	BT	✓	C1	×	BT	✓
V2	VC	BT	✓	L2	LGD	BT	✓	S2	SGD	BT	✓	C2	×	BT	×
V3	VC-Side	×	✓	L3	LGD-End	×	✓	S3	SGD-End	×	✓	C3	×	×	✓
V4	VC-Side	BT	×	L4	LGD-End	BT	×	S4	SGD-End	BT	×	C4	×	ST	×
V5	VC	BT	×	L5	LGD	BT	×	S5	SGD	BT	×	C5	×	×	×
V6	VC	×	✓	L6	LGD	×	✓	S6	SGD	×	✓				
V7	VC-Side	×	×	L7	LGD-End	×	×	S7	SGD-End	×	×				
V8	VC	×	×	L8	LGD	×	×	S8	SGD	×	×				

TABLE II
RESULTS FOR CRCG ON $CRCN_{short}$ WITH DIFFERENT FACTOR SETTINGS ON BOTH PARADIGMS.

ID	Fine-tuning on Pre-trained Models (CodeT5)						Prompting on Large Language Models (GPT-4)*					
	Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)			Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)		
	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1
V1	5.99	11.74	8.89	8.46	-4.03	1.28	3.97	10.28	11.02	-3.38	3.87	-0.05
V2	6.04	11.74	8.85	9.24	-4.39	1.40	3.97	9.98	10.82	-3.10	3.75	0.05
V3	5.10	10.16	7.74	8.34	-5.98	0.13	3.46	9.09	9.95	-4.94	2.94	-1.30
V4	5.99	11.78	8.86	9.69	-4.14	1.72	3.92	9.94	10.44	-3.30	4.20	0.14
V5	5.97	11.70	8.78	10.08	-3.93	2.01	4.10	9.98	10.70	-2.62	3.68	0.23
V6	5.05	9.98	7.52	7.19	-5.55	-0.09	3.41	8.23	9.22	-4.78	1.98	-1.68
V7	5.07	10.29	7.39	10.79	-5.65	1.42	3.53	8.86	9.92	-4.25	3.16	-0.80
V8	5.06	10.11	7.63	9.00	-6.06	0.38	3.56	8.24	9.13	-3.28	2.06	-0.84
L1	6.00	11.66	8.68	8.24	-3.89	1.26	3.75	9.67	10.72	-3.96	3.71	-0.43
L2	5.96	11.62	8.70	8.37	-4.35	1.06	3.82	9.84	10.54	-3.83	3.31	-0.58
L3	5.15	10.21	7.48	9.79	-5.53	1.05	3.46	8.79	9.73	-5.11	2.88	-1.40
L4	5.97	11.59	8.66	8.18	-4.63	0.81	3.83	9.64	10.38	-3.20	3.10	-0.30
L5	5.94	11.64	8.59	8.59	-4.05	1.33	4.07	9.71	10.32	-2.29	3.52	0.36
L6	5.17	10.18	7.50	9.69	-5.40	1.08	3.38	8.62	9.88	-5.11	2.81	-1.44
L7	5.17	10.30	7.61	10.54	-4.98	1.70	3.53	8.81	9.63	-4.01	2.58	-0.97
L8	5.15	10.27	7.59	10.51	-5.43	1.42	3.56	8.89	9.68	-4.12	3.05	-0.80
S1	5.96	11.62	8.66	8.00	-4.71	0.69	3.75	9.58	10.52	-3.76	3.30	-0.52
S2	5.91	11.68	8.68	8.66	-4.62	1.02	3.65	9.56	10.47	-3.83	3.53	-0.44
S3	5.20	10.15	7.43	8.87	-6.01	0.33	3.33	8.90	10.04	-5.56	2.59	-1.78
S4	5.92	11.53	8.55	8.00	-5.17	0.40	3.88	9.58	10.35	-3.39	3.21	-0.39
S5	5.93	11.57	8.50	10.00	-4.36	1.76	3.91	9.92	10.85	-2.92	3.58	0.05
S6	5.17	10.12	7.46	9.19	-5.73	0.64	3.38	8.97	10.17	-5.27	2.45	-1.70
S7	5.16	10.16	7.51	9.51	-5.98	0.63	3.52	8.91	9.87	-4.75	3.09	-1.12
S8	5.12	10.07	7.44	8.94	-5.65	0.60	3.39	8.52	9.77	-4.38	2.64	-1.11
C1	6.05	11.62	8.49	8.64	-4.89	0.85	4.20	10.28	10.86	-2.31	3.61	0.36
C2	5.83	11.36	8.46	7.73	-4.86	0.49	4.05	9.68	10.22	-1.54	3.00	0.47
C3	4.88	9.85	7.08	11.12	-7.54	0.45	3.56	8.72	9.61	-3.47	2.65	-0.67
C4	5.77	11.37	8.48	7.82	-4.98	0.46	3.55	8.38	9.19	-2.95	2.08	-0.65
C5	4.85	9.82	7.00	10.75	-7.34	0.40	3.74	8.74	9.54	-1.90	2.17	-0.13

TABLE III
RESULTS FOR CRCG ON $CRCN_{long}$ WITH DIFFERENT FACTOR SETTINGS ON BOTH PARADIGMS.

ID	Fine-tuning on Pre-trained Models (CodeT5)						Prompting on Large Language Models (GPT-4)*					
	Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)			Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)		
	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1
V4	6.14	12.05	8.95	9.45	-4.36	1.48	4.01	10.24	11.24	-3.39	4.39	0.22
L5	6.32	12.32	9.18	9.35	-3.72	1.81	4.05	9.75	10.70	-2.77	3.68	0.19
S5	6.17	12.03	9.03	8.94	-3.79	1.59	3.79	9.69	11.00	-3.83	3.62	-0.40
C2	6.12	12.10	9.02	9.02	-4.35	1.29	4.22	9.86	10.52	-1.43	3.33	0.71
C4	5.97	11.82	8.90	8.34	-3.98	1.23	3.55	8.56	9.62	-3.05	2.49	-0.47
C5	4.97	10.26	7.76	11.81	-5.44	1.88	3.86	9.07	9.87	-1.81	2.49	0.11

TABLE IV
ABSOLUTE AND RELATIVE AVERAGE TOKEN LENGTH OF DIFFERENT SETTINGS ON $CRCN_{short}$.

ID	Avg. Token Len.										
	Abs.	Rel.									
V1	183.51	1.58	L1	186.36	1.60	S1	161.95	1.39	C1	144.61	1.24
V2	179.51	1.54	L2	172.29	1.48	S2	158.46	1.36	C2	118.27	1.02
V3	181.51	1.56	L3	184.36	1.59	S3	159.95	1.38	C3	142.61	1.23
V4	150.52	1.30	L4	158.21	1.36	S4	134.75	1.16	C4	118.09	1.02
V5	146.52	1.26	L5	144.14	1.24	S5	131.26	1.13	C5	116.22	1.00
V6	177.51	1.53	L6	170.29	1.47	S6	156.46	1.35			
V7	148.46	1.28	L7	156.21	1.34	S7	132.71	1.14			
V8	144.46	1.24	L8	142.14	1.22	S8	129.22	1.11			

TABLE V
ABSOLUTE AND RELATIVE AVERAGE TOKEN LENGTH OF DIFFERENT SETTINGS ON $CRCN_{long}$.

ID	Avg. Token Length		ID	Avg. Token Length		ID	Avg. Token Length	
	Absolute	Relative		Absolute	Relative		Absolute	Relative
V4	232.60	1.45	S5	179.29	1.12	C4	162.41	1.02
L5	198.13	1.24	C2	162.04	1.01	C5	159.98	1.00

TABLE VI
THE RESULTS FOR ADDING A CHANGE-AWARE GRAPH AS AN ADDITIONAL COMPONENT ON $CRCN_{short}$.

ID	CodeT5 without Graph						CodeT5 with Change-aware Graph					
	Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)			Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)		
	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1
V4	5.99	11.78	8.86	9.69	-4.14	1.72	6.58	11.09	9.10	-5.55	-6.40	-7.16
L5	5.94	11.64	8.59	8.59	-4.05	1.33	6.60	11.03	9.19	-6.82	-6.59	-7.95
S5	5.93	11.57	8.50	10.00	-4.36	1.76	6.59	11.00	9.19	-8.34	-6.68	-8.76
C2	5.83	11.36	8.46	7.73	-4.86	0.49	6.67	11.08	9.27	-7.97	-6.58	-8.52

TABLE VII
THE RESULTS FOR ADDING A CHANGE-AWARE GRAPH AS AN ADDITIONAL COMPONENT ON $CRCN_{long}$.

ID	CodeT5 without Graph						CodeT5 with Change-aware Graph					
	Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)			Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)		
	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1
V4	6.14	12.05	8.95	9.45	-4.36	1.48	6.70	11.19	9.40	-8.93	-6.74	-9.21
L5	6.32	12.32	9.18	9.35	-3.72	1.81	6.86	11.56	9.49	-5.65	-5.94	-7.07
S5	6.17	12.03	9.03	8.94	-3.79	1.59	6.74	11.30	9.36	-7.44	-6.24	-8.08
C2	6.12	12.10	9.02	9.02	-4.35	1.29	6.76	11.30	9.47	-9.23	-6.51	-9.16

TABLE VIII
THE RESULTS OF BASELINES AND ABOVE BEST APPROACHES.

ID	$CRCN_{short}$						$CRCN_{long}$					
	Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)			Syntactic Similarity			Semantic Similarity (BERTScore)		
	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1	BLEU	ROUGE	METEOR	P	R	F1
Tufano	5.66	9.68	9.70	-7.91	-2.83	-6.48	6.25	10.41	10.42	-7.02	-1.76	-5.51
AUGER	3.27	7.69	4.30	-8.41	-13.38	-11.44	3.29	7.83	4.40	-7.70	-12.83	-10.83
CFer	3.44	6.33	6.65	-7.07	-8.00	-8.01	3.43	6.45	6.78	-6.96	-7.54	-7.74
CRer	5.26	10.75	8.82	10.38	-3.13	2.60	5.33	10.72	8.11	7.95	-4.63	0.67
Best	6.67	11.78	11.02	11.12	4.20	2.01	6.86	12.32	11.24	11.81	4.39	1.88